

SCiPAD

Skin care interventions for preventing eczema and food allergy: a
systematic review and individual participant data meta-analysis

Statistical Analysis Plan

Version 2

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1. Description of the study

1.1 Study design

This study is a systematic review and individual participant data (IPD) meta-analysis of skin care interventions for the prevention of eczema and food allergy. The overarching aim of the IPD meta-analysis is to determine whether interventions such as moisturisers or other approaches for improving the skin barrier of babies during the first year of life can prevent eczema or food allergy.

This statistical analysis plan is an extended version of the statistical analysis plan described in the published versions of the study Protocol (1, 2). This analysis plan provides details on the analysis strategy, variable construction and statistical testing procedures and is the definitive statistical analysis plan to be implemented in this study.

1.2 Background and study rationale

A full description of the study background and rationale for assessing the effectiveness of skin care interventions for the prevention of eczema and food allergy can be found in the study protocol (1, 2). We will include individual participant data (IPD) meta-analysis within this review because this will enable us to (i) fit a consistent analysis model to all trial data sets to ensure we are comparing treatment effects which are adjusted for the same covariates across trials, (ii) obtain more reliable and powerful subgroup analyses to identify patient or study factors associated with treatment response, and (iii) to explore treatment efficacy by evaluating the relationship between compliance with the intervention and the outcomes of interest. This systematic review also incorporates prospectively planned meta-analysis (PPMA). This involves planning the details of the meta-analysis before the results of each individual trial are known. Prospective meta-analysis reduces bias related to knowledge of existing trial outcomes, which might influence study selection and design in a retrospective study. It also allows for streamlining of the design of the individual trials so that the timing of endpoints can be aligned, and outcomes are standardised across trials.

1.3 Principal research objectives to be addressed

The following objectives will be investigated:

Aim 1: To ascertain if skin care interventions, commenced in early infancy, influence the risk of developing eczema or food allergy

Aim 2: To identify features of the study populations such as age, hereditary risk and adherence to the interventions, which are associated with the greatest treatment benefit or harm for both eczema and food allergy.

1.4 Types of trials to be included

Parallel group or factorial randomised controlled trials (RCTs) will be included. Both individual and cluster randomised trials will also be included. Quasi-randomised controlled trials or observational studies will not be included.

1.5 Types of participants to be included

Infants (age ≤ 12 months) will be included. Infants who have already been diagnosed with eczema or food allergy at the time of randomisation will not be included. Study populations defined by a pre-existing health state in the infant, such as preterm birth (less than 37 weeks gestation) or congenital skin conditions will also not be included, since findings in these populations may not be generalisable.

We will attempt to obtain individual participant data (IPD) data for all included studies. If IPD data are not available, aggregate data will be obtained instead. For studies with only aggregate data available, we will exclude the whole individual study if some participants are not eligible, unless ineligible participants make up an insignificant proportion of that trials total group, $< 5\%$.

1.6 Types of interventions to be included

All skin care interventions that could potentially enhance skin barrier function, reduce dryness or reduce subclinical inflammation will be included. These include:

- moisturisers/emollients,
- bathing products (which may include oils or emollients),
- other skin care advice such as reducing soap exposure or changing bathing frequency,
- use of water softeners.

Some will be simple single interventions, while others are likely to be complex interventions that utilise a combination of measures to protect or promote skin barrier function, hydration or reduce subclinical inflammation. If treatment of clinically apparent eczema or other interventions which don't directly focus on skin barrier is the main intervention, with promotion of skin barrier function prior to the development of eczema only being a minor component of the intervention, then the trial will not be eligible for inclusion.

The comparator will be no treatment intervention/advice or standard care in the study setting.

Subgroup analyses (see Section 4.5) will separately explore the effects of interventions aimed at reducing skin damage (e.g. reduced exposure to soaps, wipes, bathing, hard water) versus interventions aimed at repairing a damaged skin barrier (e.g. emollient cream, lotion, ointment, oil). And depending on the obtained data we may be able to explore by type and/or dose (e.g. in grams) of emollient.

Multifaceted interventions where the skin care component is only a small part of the study will be excluded if the skin care component is likely trivial or irrelevant to the outcome.

1.7 Primary outcomes

There will be two co-primary outcomes:

- (1) Eczema by age 1-3 years using the closest available time point to 2 years, from each included trial. Where multiple measures of eczema are reported the hierarchy of diagnosis for the primary analysis will be (i) using published, validated criteria, with preference given to Hanifin & Rajka or UK Working Party or other modifications to Hanifin & Rajka, where more than one set of criteria is reported (ii) doctor diagnosis of eczema then (iii) parent report of eczema.
- (2) Food allergy by age 1-3 years using the closest available time point to 2 years, from each included trial. Where multiple measures of food allergy are reported the hierarchy of diagnosis for the primary analysis will be (i) confirmed IgE mediated food allergy diagnosis made using oral food challenge followed by (ii) investigator assessment using a combination of allergy testing and clinical history. The primary foods of interest are milk, egg and peanut however we will collect all available data on any foods that are available from each study.

If multiple measures of eczema are identified across trials a sensitivity analysis is planned to separately look at eczema measured using the UK Working Party Criteria, or other variations of the Hanifin and Rajka criteria only. Additionally if multiple measures of food allergy assessment are identified we will separately look at food allergy measured using secure diagnosis of food allergy by oral food challenge only.

1.8 Secondary outcomes

The secondary outcomes are:

- Adverse events during intervention period, including (i) slippage accidents around the time of bathing or application of moisturiser; (ii) skin infection during the

intervention period; (iii) stinging or allergic reactions to moisturisers and (iv) any other serious adverse events recorded.

- Eczema severity - clinician assessed using EASI (3) (Eczema area and severity index) or similar validated method at age 1-3 years using the closest available time point to 2 years, from each included trial.
- Parent reported eczema severity using POEM (Patient orientated eczema measure) (4) or similar validated patient reported measure at age 1-3 years using the closest available time point to 2 years, from each included trial.
- Time to onset of eczema
- Parent report of immediate (<2hours) reaction to a known food allergen, by age 1-3 years using the closest available time point to 2 years, from each included trial (using trial specific definition for immediate reaction); known food allergens are milk, soya, wheat, fish, seafood, peanut, tree nut, egg or a local common food allergen.
- Allergic sensitisation to foods and inhalants via skin prick test (or if not available, via Specific Immunoglobulin E) by age 1-3 years using the closest available time point to 2 years, from each included trial. In the first instance, we will use the trial specific thresholds to define sensitisation for skin prick tests and Specific Immunoglobulin Es. In the absence of any trial specific guidelines we will use European Academy of Allergy and Clinical Immunology definitions of sensitisation, i.e. skin prick test $\geq 3\text{mm}$ and Specific Immunoglobulin E $\geq 0.35\text{kua/L}$.

1.9 Brief description of proposed analysis strategy and blinding

We will conduct an individual patient data (IPD) meta-analysis of both prospective and retrospectively acquired data. Primary meta-analysis will use all data, including IPD where available and aggregate data used where IPD could not be provided. A sensitivity analysis of trials providing IPD only will be performed. If however aggregate data represents only an insignificant proportion of the total dataset for example <10%, then the primary analysis will be on IPD data only. In this scenario we will undertake a sensitivity analysis adding in the aggregate data.

We will undertake prospectively planned meta-analysis (PPMA) of a more limited number of trials, as a sensitivity analysis. PPMA will be limited to those trials where the study authors were not aware of study outcomes at the time of PPMA protocol registration on PROSPERO (10th February 2017) and submission of the Cochrane protocol (February 2019). PPMA reduces bias related to knowledge of existing trial outcomes, which might influence study selection in a retrospective study, since studies are included without any knowledge of outcome. Additionally outcomes across the prospectively planned trials may be more closely aligned due to awareness of being included in this IPD meta-analysis. The prospective meta-analysis will be conducted using the same approach to the primary analysis (i.e. IPD only or IPD plus aggregate data dependent on amount of aggregate data, see above).

Analyses will estimate the effect of being assigned to receive the intervention. For all analyses, unless otherwise specified, we will retain all participants eligible in the treatment group to which they were originally assigned who have an outcome,

irrespective of the treatment they actually received (i.e. an intention-to-treat analysis). Excluding only those who don't fulfil our eligibility criteria at baseline will not introduce bias as the decision to remove such patients is not influenced by events that occurred after randomisation. Subgroup analyses will investigate whether patient characteristics are associated with the intervention effect via tests of treatment interactions. We will also investigate the treatment effect by study characteristics including intervention type and the effect of complying with the intervention.

All treatment estimates will be accompanied by confidence intervals, which will be 2-sided and at the 95% level.

Version 1 of the SAP was prepared before the assessment of any grouped outcome data when the statistician remained blind to intervention and control group outcomes for each data field, so that they could not bias this process by exploring the possible impact of different data analysis and coding decisions on findings.

2. Search methods and data extraction

2.1 Identification of eligible trials

An electronic search strategy has been developed to identify studies for inclusion (see Appendix 1). In addition to searching online databases of published research articles we will search trial registries and make contact with companies and experts in the field in order to identify ongoing studies.

Title and abstract screening will be done by two people (MK, SC or LT) to identify trials for inclusion based on the relevant inclusion criteria. Reasons for exclusions will be discussed and any discrepancies will be resolved by consensus with the aid of an additional reviewer (RB). Subsequently two authors will independently assess full-texts of publications according to the same inclusion criteria specified above (MK, SC or LT). We will record the reasons for exclusions of trials at both stages of screening. If the eligibility of a trial is unclear from the available information we will contact trial authors.

2.2 Data extraction and management

Two reviewers will extract data independently to minimise bias (MK, SC or LT). Any discrepancies will be resolved by consensus, with the aid of a third reviewer if required. For all trials we will extract and describe data on patients and interventions by means of a standardised data extraction form.

IPD will be sought for all eligible studies. One author (LT) will send a data-request email listing the variables required for the analysis (Appendix 2) to the first and corresponding author of the associated trial.

Following the completion of a data sharing agreement selected variables will be exchanged between researchers along with a data dictionary, or full data sets where the appropriate

permissions are obtained. The list of the variables required for the SCiPAD analysis that will be requested for exchange where access to the full trial data set is not provided is outlined in Appendix 2. We will also request any available related documents such as trial protocols, case report forms and statistical analysis plans. Range and consistency checks will be carried out for all data. Any missing data, obvious errors, inconsistencies between variables or extreme values will be queried and rectified with the individual trial investigators as necessary. We will also cross-check summaries of provided data with those in published reports of the trial and contact original trial authors to resolve any identified inconsistencies. IPD will be collated, checked and cleaned by one author (SC) and data clarification sought where necessary from trial authors.

For studies which do not supply IPD we will record the reason why IPD could not be made available. We will request aggregate data on our outcomes. If aggregate data cannot be obtained directly from the study authors, two authors will assess whether any relevant appropriate aggregate level data are available in the trial publication or other sources (e.g. clinical trials registry). Aggregate data will be recorded on a standardised extraction form. Any disagreements on extracted aggregate data will be discussed and resolved by consensus, including a third author if necessary.

All data will be stored on a secure dedicated network drive, restricted to study team members only. All trial participant data will be anonymised.

2.3 Ethical approval

Ethical approval for this study has been granted by Imperial College Research Ethics committee, London 18th May 2018. ICREC reference: 18IC4563.

3. Descriptive analysis plan

Before proceeding to meta-analysis we will conduct descriptive analysis of the included trials and obtained data to aid understanding.

3.1 Study selection

The number of eligible studies identified from the searching will be summarised in a PRISMA IPD study flow diagram. This will include the number of studies identified but excluded as ineligible in addition to the total number eligible for inclusion in the quantitative synthesis and the number included in the analysis - see example PRISMA flow diagram in Figure 1.

Figure 1: PRISMA IPD Flow Diagram

3.2 Characteristics of included studies

Characteristics of each included study will be summarised in a characteristics of included studies table (see dummy Table A1 in Appendix 3). Characteristics will include: Setting (including dates), Methods (study design including sample size), participant inclusion and exclusion criteria, intervention(s), comparator(s), length of follow-up, outcomes recorded, source of funding and any potential conflicts of interest and other notes of interest.

3.3. Characteristics of included participants

For each included trial characteristics of the included participants will be reported (see dummy Table A2 in Appendix 3). Patient characteristics will include:

Infant baseline characteristics: gestational age at birth, sex, birth weight, age intervention began, *FLG* genotype, ethnicity, mode of delivery (e.g. vaginal, caesarean), method of feeding (e.g. duration of exclusive breastfeeding and total duration of breastfeeding).

Family baseline characteristics: age of mother/father, ethnicity of mother/father, educational status of mother/father, socioeconomic group, singleton or multiple pregnancy, number of children living at home, whether any furry pets (cats/dogs reported separately) living in the household/living environment, mother took any antibiotics during pregnancy, mother took any regular probiotic supplements during pregnancy, smoking history of mother/father.

Family history of atopic disease: number of first degree relatives with atopic disease (0 or 1+), number of first degree relatives with eczema (0 or 1+), number of first degree relatives with food-allergy (0 or 1+).

Compliance with randomised intervention: the data to be summarised will be informed by the available data.

Non-assigned skin care: frequency of bathing, prescribed topical treatment use, other non-assigned skin care.

Food introduction: age allergenic foods (milk, egg, peanut or other common allergenic foods) introduced, age solid foods introduced.

Continuous variables will be reported as mean (SD) if approximately normally distributed or median (IQR) if non-normal. Categorical variables will be presented using frequencies and proportions of those contributing data for the specific characteristic (as a %). These summaries will be based on observations only.

3.4 Assessment of risk of bias of included studies

Risk of bias will be assessed using the most recent version of the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool 2 (5) (see example dummy Table A3 in Appendix 3). This tool is specifically for RCTs and assesses bias from five domains:

- Bias arising from the randomisation process
- Bias due to deviations from intended interventions
- Bias due to missing outcome data
- Bias in measurement of the outcome
- Bias in selection of the reported result

We will assess the risk of bias separately for all outcomes reported in the summary of findings table, i.e. Eczema (by 1-3 years using the closest time point to 2 years), food allergy (by 1-3 years using closest time point to 2 years), slippage accidents (during intervention period), skin infection (during intervention period), allergic reactions (during intervention period), time to onset eczema, parent report food allergy (by age 1-3 using the closest time point to 2 years) and allergic sensitisation (by age 1-3 using the closest time point to 2 years).

The tool is outcome-specific and each domain will be rated as 'low risk of bias', 'some concerns' or 'high risk of bias'. For bias in selection of the reported result, this will likely be low risk for all prospectively identified studies as we intend to obtain the full dataset for these studies. For bias due to deviations from intended interventions, we are interested in the effect of assignment to the interventions at baseline, regardless of whether the interventions are received as intended by an intention-to-treat analysis that includes all randomised participants.

To reach an overall 'risk of bias' judgement for a specific outcome, the following criteria will be used : Overall low risk of bias - all domains considered low risk for the specific result, Some concerns - some concerns have been raised in at least one domain for the specific result, but no domains are considered at high risk of bias, High risk of bias - at least one domain is considered high risk for the specific result OR there are some concerns for multiple domains which substantially lowers confidence in the result.

Risk of bias assessments will be conducted independently by two review authors (MK and SC), with any disagreements resolved via discussion or through arbitration with a third author (RB).

4. Inferential meta-analysis plan

4.1 Statistical considerations

4.1.1 Comparisons

The primary analysis will include all skin care interventions versus no treatment or standard or care.

Adjustments for multiple testing will not be made. Two outcomes have been designated as co-primary (eczema and food allergy). Results will be interpreted in totality and the emphasis will be on the estimated intervention effects rather than the significance tests.

In subgroup analysis (see Section 4.5), comparisons will be stratified by the type of intervention.

4.1.2 Two-stage meta-analysis approach

We will conduct all meta-analysis of all IPD using a two-stage meta-analysis approach. This entails first estimating the treatment effect of interest within each study providing IPD using the analysis methods outlined in Sections 4.2 to 4.6. Treatment effects from trials included in this review may differ slightly from previous reports because we will be treating data in a consistent manner across all trials. Pooled treatment effects will then be computed by using standard meta-analysis approaches. That is we will employ a random effects inverse variance meta-analysis model.

We will aim to obtain IPD from all included studies, however this may not be possible in all cases. If aggregate data represents only an insignificant proportion of the entire dataset (< 10% total participants across studies), then the primary analysis will be on IPD data only. In this scenario we will undertake a sensitivity analysis adding in the aggregate data (see Section 4.4).

If aggregate data represent >10% of the data set then the primary analysis will be on IPD + aggregate data. In this case, following estimation of the treatment effect of interest within each study for each study providing IPD, in the stage 2 analysis we will combine aggregate data results with the IPD results. In this scenario we will undertake a sensitivity analysis excluding the aggregate data (see Section 4.4). Aggregate data results will be eligible for inclusion if they are unadjusted or adjusted for the same variables specified for inclusion in the stage 1 models.

We will include both prospectively planned and retrospectively acquired data in the primary analysis. We will undertake prospectively planned meta-analysis (PPMA) of a more limited number of trials, as a sensitivity analysis (see Section 4.4). PPMA will be limited to those trials where the study authors were not aware of study outcomes at the time of PPMA protocol registration on PROSPERO and submission of the Cochrane protocol.

4.1.3 Covariate adjustment

It is planned that all primary and secondary analyses will be adjusted for sex and family history of atopic disease (0 or 1+ family members – using individual trials definition of atopic disease). Since all included studies will be randomised trials these factors are not expected to vary across intervention groups. However, adjusting for these important prognostic

variables will allow us to obtain a more precise intervention effect (smaller standard errors). If one or more studies providing IPD do not provide data on either (or both) of these variables we will not perform adjustment for the associated variable (or variables) within the primary analysis, since this would mean excluding an entire study from the analysis. Where one or more trials are systematically missing all values for sex and/or family history of atopic disease and these are not adjusted for in the primary analysis an additional sensitivity analysis will be performed using multiple imputation to impute missing covariate values across trials using a latent normal model using the jomo package in R (6). The imputation model will include all the partially observed variables as responses and the completely observed ones. We will run 25 imputations. The results across multiply imputed data will be combined using Rubin's rules for each trial with data multiply imputed.

4.1.3 Assessment of heterogeneity

Both clinical and statistical heterogeneity will be examined and a pooled effect will only be generated where the data are judged to provide a meaningful summary. Clinical heterogeneity will be assessed by examining the characteristics of included participants, types of interventions, primary and secondary outcomes and follow-up period. We will use the I^2 statistic to quantify the degree of statistical heterogeneity of measures judged as suitable for meta-analysis. We will bear in mind the magnitude and direction of effects and the strength of evidence for heterogeneity based on confidence interval for I^2 to inform the exploration for heterogeneity. Where I^2 is high (e.g. over 75% or I^2 and its 95% CI suggest heterogeneity) we will explore reasons for heterogeneity including, where appropriate, sensitivity analysis excluding any studies identified as outliers (see Section 4.4) and we will carefully consider whether presenting pooled estimates is appropriate (7).

4.1.4 Unit of analysis issues

This review will include randomised controlled trials only. Factorial and cluster randomisation can be included. For factorial randomised trials, if there is a significant interaction between the two active interventions with respect to our primary outcome, then we will only include the arms 'skin care intervention/control' versus 'control/control'. In such scenarios where an interaction is present an additional sensitivity analysis will explore the impact of including data from all arms of factorial trials, with adjustment for the non-skin barrier intervention in stage 1 for the factorial trial.

Cross-over trials will not be included as the design is inappropriate for answering this clinical question. For studies with more than two treatment arms which could have multiple intervention groups in a particular meta-analysis we will combine all relevant intervention groups into a single group and all relevant control groups into a single control group.

For cluster randomised trials, mixed models that allow analysis at the level of the individual while accounting for the clustering in the data will be used for all stage 1 analyses.

4.1.5 *Dealing with missing data*

To resolve missing information about methodological properties of identified trials we will contact authors of the included trials. Where the authors are unable to provide the required information, we will rate the relevant risk of bias criterion as per the advice in the Cochrane Handbook and Risk of Bias 2.0 guidance notes, with explanation.

We do not anticipate substantial amounts of missing data for the primary outcomes. For trials providing IPD, missing patient data will naturally be handled under the assumption of missing-at-random within each trial analysis.

If there is sporadic missing data across trials for baseline covariates that we plan to adjust for we will impute missing values within studies, using the mean outcome value calculated from the non-missing values using pooled data across all treatment groups of that trial. This technique improves the statistical efficiency in the estimation of treatment effect and is justifiable since within each trial randomisation ensures that baselines are independent of treatment group (8, 9).

If one or more trials are systematically missing all values for a particular baseline covariate which we have pre-specified that we will adjust for (sex or family history of atopic disease) as specified in Section 4.1.4, we will exclude the associated covariate from the analysis model for the primary and secondary analyses. Where data allows, a subsequent additional sensitivity analysis using multiple imputation (described in Section 4.1.4) will explore the impact of adjustment for sex and family history).

For trials which do not provide IPD and report a mean difference but no standard deviation (SD) or other statistic that can be used to derive the SD we will use imputation (10). Specifically, we will impute SD's for each outcome as the pooled SD across all other trials within the same meta-analysis by treatment group. This is an appropriate method of analysis if the majority of trials do not have missing SDs in the meta-analysis. If a large proportion of trials (e.g. $\geq 20\%$) are missing data on parameter variability for a particular outcome, imputation will not be appropriate and analysis will be conducted using only the trials providing complete data and implications of this will be discussed alongside results.

Studies with substantial amounts of missing data (e.g. $\geq 20\%$ participants missing) will be included. To investigate the robustness of results sensitivity analysis will be performed excluding any studies of high risk of bias or some concerns of bias which will include the exclusion of studies with substantial amounts of missing data.

4.1.6 *Assessment of reporting biases*

By aiming to include as many prospective studies as possible in this review, as well as IPD, the risk of reporting bias and publication bias should be reduced. However, when there are at least 10 studies included in the meta-analysis we will use funnel plots to explore the likelihood of any reporting bias or small study effects (see example dummy funnel plot in Figure A1, Appendix 3). We will assess funnel plot asymmetry visually and use formal tests for funnel plot asymmetry. For continuous outcomes we will use the test proposed by Egger

et al (11). For dichotomous outcomes we will use the test proposed by Rucker et al. (12) when estimated between-study heterogeneity variance of log odds ratios, tau-squared, is more than 0.1; otherwise, when the heterogeneity variance tau-squared is less than 0.1, one of the tests proposed by Harbord et al (13) will be used. If asymmetry is detected in any of these tests or is suggested by a visual assessment we will explore and discuss possible explanations. We will also search clinical trial registries in order to identify trials which should have published or provided data but have not done so, in order to understand reporting bias at the whole trial level.

4.1.7 Measures of treatment effect

For binary outcomes where meta-analysis is considered appropriate we will calculate risk ratios. For continuous outcomes where the same measurement scale is used we will calculate the mean difference (MD), when different measurement scales are used the standardised mean difference (SMD) will be calculated. For time-to-event outcomes the intervention effect will be expressed as a hazard ratio (HR). For each outcome a 95% confidence interval (95% CI) will also be computed.

4.2 Analysis of co-primary outcomes

4.2.1 Primary analysis for eczema

Outcome Definition: Eczema

The stage 1 model, fitted to each trial providing IPD separately to estimate the trial specific Relative Risk (RR) of eczema, will be a binomial regression model. In addition to the treatment group variable indicating use of skin care intervention we will include adjustment for sex and family history of atopic disease (0 or 1+) within the stage 1 models. If there is ≥ 1 trial systematically missing all values for a particular baseline covariate which we have pre-specified baseline adjustment for (sex or family history of atopic disease) as specified in Section 4.1.4 we will exclude the associated covariate from the stage 1 analysis model. In the second stage the derived treatment effects will be combined using a random effects inverse variance model. The pooled RR for eczema will be obtained with an associated 95% confidence interval. Results will be displayed graphically in a forest plot (see example dummy forest plot, Figure A2 in Appendix 3).

4.2.2 Primary analysis for food allergy

Outcome Definition: food allergy

The stage 1 model, fitted to each trial providing IPD separately to estimate the trial specific Relative Risk (RR) of food allergy, will be a binomial regression model. In addition to the treatment group variable indicating use of skin care intervention we will include adjustment for sex and family history of atopic disease (0 or 1+) within the stage 1 models. If there is ≥ 1

trial systematically missing all values for a particular baseline covariate which we have pre-specified baseline adjustment for (sex or family history) as specified in Section 4.1.4 we will exclude the associated covariate from the stage 1 analysis model. In the second stage the derived treatment effects will be combined using a random effects inverse variance model. The pooled RR for food allergy will be obtained with an associated 95% confidence interval. Results will be displayed graphically in a forest plot (see example dummy forest plot, Figure A2 in Appendix 3).

4.3 Analysis of secondary outcomes

Summary of findings tables will display the results of all primary and key secondary outcomes including GRADE assessment of certainty (see example dummy Table A4 in Appendix 3).

4.3.1 Adverse events

Outcome Definition: Adverse events of interest during the intervention period include (i) slippage accidents around the time of bathing or application of moisturiser; (ii) skin infection during the intervention period; (iii) stinging or allergic reactions to moisturisers or; (iv) other serious adverse events.

Analysis: For outcomes (i), (ii) and (iii) the stage 1 model, fitted to each trial providing IPD separately to estimate the trial specific Relative Risk (RR) of the associated adverse event, will be a binomial regression model. In addition to the treatment group variable indicating use of skin care intervention we will include adjustment for sex and family history of atopic disease (0 or 1+) within the stage 1 models. If there is ≥ 1 trial systematically missing all values for a particular baseline covariate which we have pre-specified baseline adjustment for (sex or family history) as specified in Section 4.1.4 we will exclude the associated covariate from the stage 1 analysis model. In the second stage the derived treatment effects will be combined using a random effects inverse variance model. For each of (i), (ii) and (iii) the pooled RR will be obtained with an associated 95% confidence interval. Results for each outcome will be displayed graphically in a forest plot (see example dummy forest plot, Figure A2 in Appendix 3).

Other serious adverse events (iv) will be descriptively analysed. A summary of the number of serious adverse events and number of patients with a serious adverse event per trial by treatment arm will be produced (see dummy Table A5 in Appendix 3). Details on the specific serious adverse events reported over all trials will also be presented by treatment arm (see dummy Table A6 in Appendix 3).

4.3.2 Eczema severity

Outcome definition: Eczema severity - clinician assessed using EASI (Eczema area and severity index) or similar validated method as very severe/severe/moderate versus clear/mild.

Analysis: The stage 1 model, fitted to each trial providing IPD separately to estimate the trial specific Relative Risk (RR) of very severe/severe/moderate eczema, will be a binomial regression model. In addition to the treatment group variable indicating use of skin care intervention we will include adjustment for sex and family history of atopic disease (0 or 1+) within the stage 1 models. If there is ≥ 1 trial systematically missing all values for a particular baseline covariate which we have pre-specified baseline adjustment for (sex or family history) as specified in Section 4.1.4 we will exclude the associated covariate from the stage 1 analysis model. In the second stage the derived treatment effects will be combined using a random effects inverse variance model. The pooled RR for very severe/severe/moderate eczema will be obtained with an associated 95% confidence interval. Results will be displayed graphically in a forest plot (see example dummy forest plot, Figure A2 in Appendix 3).

We will also look at the mean treatment group difference in eczema severity. Within this analysis the stage 1 model, fitted to each trial providing IPD to obtain the mean treatment group difference in eczema severity, will be a linear regression model. In addition to the treatment group variable indicating use of skin care intervention we will include adjustment for sex and family history of atopic disease (0 or 1+) within the stage 1 models. In the second stage the derived treatment effects will be combined using a random effects inverse variance model. If all studies have used the EASI to assess eczema severity the stage 2 model will combine the mean differences. If one or more studies has used an alternative measure of eczema severity then the stage 2 model will combine the standardized mean differences (calculated as difference in mean outcome between groups/standard deviation of outcome among participants). The pooled mean treatment group or standardised mean treatment group difference for eczema severity will be obtained with an associated 95% confidence interval. Results will be displayed graphically in a forest plot (see example dummy forest plot, Figure A3 in Appendix 3).

4.3.3 Parent reported eczema severity

Outcome definition: Parent reported eczema severity using POEM (Patient orientated eczema measure) (4) or similar validated patient reported measure as very severe/severe/moderate versus clear/mild.

Analysis: The stage 1 model, fitted to each trial providing IPD separately to estimate the trial specific Relative Risk (RR) of very severe/severe/moderate parent reported eczema, will be a binomial regression model. In addition to the treatment group variable indicating use of skin care intervention we will include adjustment for sex and family history of atopic disease (0 or 1+) within the stage 1 models. If there is ≥ 1 trial systematically missing all values for a particular baseline covariate which we have pre-specified baseline adjustment for (sex or

family history) as specified in Section 4.1.4 we will exclude the associated covariate from the stage 1 analysis model. In the second stage the derived treatment effects will be combined using a random effects inverse variance model. The pooled RR for very severe/severe/moderate eczema will be obtained with an associated 95% confidence interval. Results will be displayed graphically in a forest plot (see example dummy forest plot, Figure A2 in Appendix 3).

We will also look at the mean treatment group difference in parent reported eczema severity. The stage 1 model fitted to each trial providing IPD to obtain the mean treatment group difference in parent reported eczema severity will be a linear regression model. In addition to the treatment group variable indicating use of skin care intervention we will include adjustment for sex and family history of atopic disease (0 or 1+) within the stage 1 models. In the second stage the derived treatment effects will be combined using a random effects inverse variance model. If all studies have used the POEM to assess parent reported eczema severity then the stage 2 model will combine the mean differences. If one or more studies have used an alternative measure of parent reported eczema severity then the stage 2 model will combine the standardized mean differences (calculated as difference in mean outcome between groups/standard deviation of outcome among participants).

The pooled mean treatment group or standardised mean treatment group difference for eczema severity will be obtained with an associated 95% confidence interval. Results will be displayed graphically in a forest plot (see example dummy forest plot, Figure A3 in Appendix 3).

4.3.4 Time to onset of eczema

Outcome definition: defined as time from randomisation to time of first report of eczema. Where multiple measures of eczema are reported the hierarchy of diagnosis will be (i) investigator assessment as described by the Hanifin and Rajka criteria in their original form or the UK Working Party refinement of them (14) or other modifications of the Hanifin and Rajka criteria, (ii) doctor diagnosis of eczema then (iii) parent report of eczema

Analysis: Since outcomes are observed at a relatively few discrete time intervals the stage 1 model fitted to each trial providing IPD will be a binomial regression model with a complementary log-log link, where follow-up time has been split into appropriate intervals, for example as 3 intervals (3 months, 6 months, 12 months). This model is appropriate for discrete time-to-event data. In addition to the treatment group variable indicating use of skin care intervention we will include adjustment for sex and family history of atopic disease (0 or 1+) within the stage 1 models. If there is ≥ 1 trial systematically missing all values for a particular baseline covariate which we have pre-specified baseline adjustment for (sex or family history) as specified in Section 4.1.4 we will exclude the associated covariate from the stage 1 analysis model. The exponentiated regression coefficient for treatment can be interpreted as a hazard ratio (HR) for treatment in continuous time. Only trials which record eczema at the included intervals e.g. 3, 6 and 12 months or in continuous time (which can be categorised into the selected pre-specified intervals) will be included. The included intervals will be confirmed following blinded data review to maximise the number of participants included within this analysis.

In the second stage the derived treatment effects will be combined using a random effects inverse variance model. The pooled HR will be obtained with an associated 95% confidence interval. Results will be displayed graphically in a forest plot (see example dummy forest plot, Figure A4 in Appendix 3).

Since follow-up time points for eczema will vary between trials and not all trials will be eligible for inclusion within the described time to onset of eczema meta-analysis, we will also descriptively report the proportions of individuals with eczema over time across all trials by trial and treatment arm (see example dummy Table A7 in Appendix 3).

4.3.5 Parent reported immediate reaction to a known food allergen

Outcome definition: Parent report of immediate (<2hours) reaction to at least one known food allergen; milk, soya, wheat, fish, seafood, peanut, tree nut, egg or local common food allergen

Analysis: The stage 1 model, fitted to each trial providing IPD separately to estimate the RR of parent reported immediate reaction to a known food allergy, will be a binomial regression model. In addition to the treatment group variable indicating use of skin care intervention we will include adjustment for sex and family history of atopic disease (0 or 1+) within the stage 1 models. If there is ≥ 1 trial systematically missing all values for a particular baseline covariate which we have pre-specified baseline adjustment for (sex or family history) as specified in Section 4.1.4 we will exclude the associated covariate from the stage 1 analysis model. In the second stage the derived treatment effects will be combined using a random effects inverse variance model. The pooled RR for parent reported immediate reaction to a known food allergy will be obtained with an associated 95% confidence interval. Results will be displayed graphically in a forest plot (see example dummy forest plot, Figure A2 in Appendix 3).

The same analysis model will also be used to assess the treatment group difference for each of milk, egg, peanut and other food allergens separately (see example dummy Table A8 in Appendix 3). Results will also be displayed graphically in a forest plot (see example dummy forest plot, Figure A2 in Appendix 3).

4.3.6 Allergic sensitisation to foods and inhalants

Outcome definition: Allergic sensitisation to any foods or inhalant via skin prick test (or if not available, via Specific Immunoglobulin E).

Analysis: The stage 1 model, fitted to each trial providing IPD separately to estimate the RR of allergic sensation to any food or inhalants, will be a binomial regression model. In addition to the treatment group variable indicating use of skin care intervention we will

include adjustment for sex and family history of atopic disease (0 or 1+) within the stage 1 models. If there is ≥ 1 trial systematically missing all values for a particular baseline covariate which we have pre-specified baseline adjustment for (sex or family history) as specified in Section 4.1.4 we will exclude the associated covariate from the stage 1 analysis model. In the second stage the derived treatment effects will be combined using a random effects inverse variance model. The pooled RR for allergic sensation to any food or inhalants will be obtained with an associated 95% confidence interval. Results will be displayed graphically in a forest plot (see example dummy forest plot, Figure A2 in Appendix 3).

The same analysis model will also be used to assess the treatment group difference for any food and any inhalant separately and also separately for milk, egg and peanut (see example dummy Table A9 in Appendix 3).

4.4 Sensitivity analysis

We will conduct the following *a priori* planned sensitivity analyses to assess the robustness of the meta-analysis results for the co-primary outcomes (see dummy Table A10 in Appendix 3).

4.4.1 By risk of bias

We will aim to include all studies regardless of risk of bias in the primary analysis, and will undertake a sensitivity analysis of studies, including only studies which are assessed as having a low risk of bias. The low risk of bias sensitivity analysis will exclude studies at high or risk of bias or those with some concerns for the overall Cochrane Risk of Bias tool 2.0 risk of bias.

4.4.2 By outcome definition

We will explore the impact of using different definitions of outcome measures by undertaking sensitivity analyses of only outcomes that have previously been validated. For the co-primary outcome of eczema, in the absence of agreed core outcomes, we will undertake sensitivity analysis of eczema evaluated by using the UK Working Party Criteria, or other variations of the Hanifin and Rajka criteria only.

For food allergy we will again undertake sensitivity analysis for secure diagnosis of food allergy by oral food challenge.

4.4.3 Excluding/including aggregate data

Analysis will exclude/include aggregate studies that do not provide IPD based on the approach adopted for primary analysis (see Section 1.9). If aggregate data represents only an insignificant proportion of the dataset for example $<10\%$, then the primary analysis will be on IPD data only. In this scenario we will undertake a sensitivity analysis adding in the aggregate data. Otherwise primary analysis will include IPD and aggregate data and sensitivity analyses will exclude the aggregate data.

4.4.4 Excluding non-prospectively acquired data

A sensitivity analysis will exclude any data that is not prospectively required. Prospectively acquired data is data which were not known to their study Chief Investigator, in analysed and unblinded form, prior to 10th February 2017.

4.4.5 To explore heterogeneity

Where considerable statistical heterogeneity is observed (e.g. $I^2 > 75\%$ or I^2 and its 95% CI suggest heterogeneity) we will explore reasons for heterogeneity and where appropriate conduct sensitivity analysis excluding any studies identified as outlying. Outlying studies are those with very different study findings to others reporting comparable interventions/outcomes. Outliers will be identified from an inspection of the individual study treatment estimates and 95% CI's in forest plots.

4.4.6 Including data from all arms of factorial studies with a significant Interaction

For factorial trials, if there is a significant interaction between the two active interventions with respect to our primary outcome, then we will only include the arms 'skin care intervention/control' versus 'control/control'. In such scenarios an additional sensitivity analysis will explore the impact of including data from all arms of factorial trials, with adjustment for the non-skin barrier intervention in stage 1 for the factorial trial.

4.5 Assessment of interactions with interventions

Assessment of interactions will be conducted for the two co-primary outcomes (see dummy Table A11 in Appendix 3). Results will be displayed in forest plots. Participant subgroups of interest which have been identified a priori for analysis are:

Comparing the effects of the intervention on "high" or "low/normal" risk for atopy based on *FLG* genotype (as 2 groups: Wild type vs one or two *FLG* null mutation(s))

Comparing the effects of the intervention on "high" or "low/normal" risk for atopy based on family history of allergic disease (≥ 1 first degree relative with history of allergic disease)

Comparing the effects of the intervention on "high" or "low/normal" risk for atopy based on *FLG* genotype (as 2 groups: Wild type vs one or two *FLG* null mutation(s)) or family history of allergic disease (≥ 1 first degree relative with history of allergic disease)

Subgroup effects for the participant level characteristics on the two primary outcomes will be calculated by first estimating treatment by covariate interaction terms within studies using the individual participant data. The interaction terms will then be combined across

studies in the same way as for the main intervention effects, using a random effects inverse variance meta-analysis.

Subgroup analysis will also be performed for the following 'by study' characteristics:

By Intervention type:

We will compare the effect of interventions aimed at reducing skin damage only (e.g. reduced exposure to soaps, wipes, bathing, hard water) versus control against the effect of interventions aimed at repairing a damaged skin barrier only (e.g. emollient cream, lotion, ointment, oil) versus control. A summary of findings table will display the results of all primary and key secondary outcomes including grade assessment for each of these two comparisons separated by intervention type (see example dummy Table A12-13 in Appendix 3).

Depending on the obtained data we may explore by type and/or dose (e.g. in grams) of emollient.

By Intervention timing:

We will compare the effect of all interventions on those participants advised to commence the skin care intervention within the first 4 weeks of life against control and of those who commenced intervention after 4 weeks against control.

By Intervention duration:

We will compare the effect of all 'short' interventions against control, where 'short' is regarded as up to 6 months of treatment and 'longer' treatment durations, of 6 months duration or more against control.

For 'by study' level characteristics, treatment effects will be pooled separately for each characteristic level and a test for subgroup differences will be performed using a chi-squared test.

4.6 Supplementary analysis to estimate Complier Average Causal Effect

To explore the impact of compliance we will estimate the effect of complying with the intended intervention. For the subgroup of trials providing compliance data we will estimate the complier average causal effect (CACE) for each co-primary outcome. As in the primary analysis a two stage approach to analysis will be followed. For each trial the CACE will be estimated using instrumental variable (IV) analysis.

Randomisation will be used as an instrumental variable for intervention received and the CACE will be estimated using a two-stage residual inclusion estimator approach (2SRI) (Cook

2018). Randomisation meets the criteria for an adequate instrument since (i) randomisation predicts the treatment receipt, (ii) randomisation is unconfounded with the outcome and we assume (iii) no direct effect of randomisation on the outcome (other than via treatment receipt) – *the exclusion restriction*. Here, we will initially define a ‘complier’ using the individual trials definition of a complier. If unavailable the definition of a ‘complier’ will be informed by the definition of a complier in other included trials. Where interventions and the quality of compliance data are sufficiently comparable random effects models will be used in stage 2 to derive the pooled CACE effect. Results will be displayed in a forest plot (see example forest plot in Figure A2 in Appendix 3). The primary analysis will be repeated for each of the trials in the subgroup of trials with compliance data and we will compare the pooled CACE estimates against the primary treatment effect (RR) estimating the effect of being assigned to the intervention for the subgroup of trials where compliance data is available. Subsequently we will explore the impact of different threshold values for defining compliance.

We will only be able to confirm alternative thresholds for compliance once data has been collected, and we are aware of the available data fields on compliance. Prior to the commencement of any meta-analysis, we plan to hold a SCiPAD investigators meeting that will be attended by clinical investigators and study analysts to establish alternative thresholds for defining compliance. Based on the data fields available, additional sensitivity analysis by prescribed treatment intensity may also be defined prior to any meta-analysis commencement.

4.7 Trial Sequential Analysis

Meta-analyses of the primary outcomes will include trial sequential analysis, using 2-sided 5% significance and 90% power to estimate optimum heterogeneity-adjusted information sizes needed to identify relative risk reductions of 20% and 30%. Control event rates will be estimated using random effects meta-analyses of the pooled proportions from the largest studies included in the meta-analyses and compared with event rates from large population-based studies. Trial sequential analysis will identify when the optimum information size or futility boundaries for pre-defined effect sizes in relation to the two co-primary outcomes have been reached.

5 Software

Stata, R or Revman will be used for data description and the main inferential analysis. Some specific Stata commands which may be used to conduct the inferential analysis have been indicated in the relevant sections. TSA will be performed using TSA software by the Copenhagen Trial Unit.

6 Amendments to SAP version 1.0

Amendments to the SAP that were made after the SAP (version 1.0) was signed off by the signatories:

Version 2.0

1. Patient inclusion criteria refined to exclude study populations defined as preterm infants < 37 weeks, following noting that there is a Cochrane Neonatal review on skin care for preterm infants <37 weeks gestation [*Topical emollient for preventing infection in preterm infants*].
2. Clarified that the prospective meta-analysis will be conducted using the same approach to the primary analysis (i.e. IPD only or IPD plus aggregate data dependent on amount of aggregate data).
3. Clarified the outcomes that the Risk of Bias assessment will be conducted for.
4. Clarified definition of categories of family history of atopy variable for adjustment as 0 or 1+ family members with atopy, using individual trials definition of atopy.

Version 2.0 was agreed and signed off when the statistician (SC) was unblinded to treatment allocations in the data received to date. This was prior to the collection of the full dataset for the SCiPAD project. The above amendments were made to version 1.0 following review of the Cochrane protocol by the Cochrane central methods support group.

7 SAP signatures

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Appendix 1 – Search strategy

1 Draft search strategy for MEDLINE (Ovid)

1. exp Emollients/
2. emollient\$.ti,ab.
3. moisturis\$.mp.
4. moisturiz\$.mp.
5. exp Skin Cream/
6. or/1-5
7. cream\$.ti,ab.
8. Emulsions/
9. emulsion\$.ti,ab.
10. exp Lubricants/
11. lubricant\$.ti,ab.
12. exp Ointments/
13. ointment\$.ti,ab.
14. lotion\$.mp.
15. exp Oils/
16. oil\$1.ti,ab.
17. (gel or gels).mp.
18. or/7-17
19. skin.ti,ab.
20. exp Skin/
21. or/19-20
22. 18 and 21
23. bath\$3.ti,ab.
24. exp Baths/
25. exp Soaps/
26. soap\$.ti,ab.
27. exp Water Softening/
28. water softener\$.ti,ab.
29. exp Skin Care/
30. or/23-29
31. 6 or 22 or 30
32. randomized controlled trial.pt.
33. controlled clinical trial.pt.
34. randomized.ab.
35. placebo.ab.
36. clinical trials as topic.sh.
37. randomly.ab.
38. trial.ti.
39. 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38
40. exp animals/ not humans.sh.
41. 39 not 40
42. exp infant/ or exp infant, newborn/
43. (Infan\$ or newborn\$ or new-born\$ or perinat\$ or neonat\$ or baby\$ or babies).mp.

44. 42 or 43

45. 31 and 41

46. 31 and 41 and 44

[Lines 32-41: Cochrane Highly sensitive search strategy for identifying randomized trials in MEDLINE: sensitivity and precision-maximizing version (2008 revision) ([Lefebvre 2011](#))]

2 Draft search strategy for clinicaltrials.gov register

emollient OR emollients OR moisturiser OR moisturisers OR moisturizer OR moisturizers OR barrier OR skin OR skincare OR bath OR bathing OR water softener OR water softeners OR water treatment

3 Draft search strategy for WHO ICTRP trials register

emollient OR emollients OR moisturiser OR moisturisers OR moisturizer OR moisturizers OR barrier OR skin OR skincare OR bath OR bathing OR water softener OR water softeners OR water treatment

Appendix 2 – Variables requested for the SCiPAD analysis: for all randomised participants

Patient identifiers for analysis inclusion

1. Unique patient ID (anonymous - or please give a new SCiPAD ID and keep log of their corresponding trial ID)
2. Randomised treatment allocation
3. Date of randomisation
4. Received randomised treatment (yes/no)
5. Included in the trials primary analysis (yes/no)

Primary outcomes:

6. Eczema (at all time points collected and using all recorded measures of eczema or eczema symptoms e.g. UK working party definition and investigator assessed – please send all eczema measures used and additional variables on skin condition (itch etc) pre formal eczema diagnosis and timepoint)
7. Food allergy (at all time points collected and using all recorded measures e.g. using oral food challenge and investigator assessed – please send all food allergy measures used)

Secondary outcomes:

8. Slippage accidents around the time of bathing or application of emollient*
9. Skin infections during the intervention period*
10. Stinging or allergies reactions to moisturisers*
11. Serious adverse events*
12. Time of eczema onset (first report of a diagnosis of eczema as a specific date or first visit date eczema recorded)
13. Eczema severity - clinician assessed: EASI or similar validated measure (at all time points collected)
14. Eczema severity - parent assessed: POEM or similar validated measure (at all time points collected)
15. Parent reported of immediate (<2hours) reaction to a known food allergen: milk, soya, wheat, fish, seafood, peanut, tree nut, egg or local common food allergen (at all time points collected and for each food allergen recorded)
16. Allergic sensitisation to foods and inhalants via skin prick test (at all time points collected and for each food and inhalant recorded)

Infant baseline characteristics:

17. Gestational age at birth
18. Sex†
19. Birth weight
20. Pre-existing health state in the infant, such as very preterm birth (less than 32 weeks gestation) or congenital skin condition
21. Infant already diagnosed with eczema at the time of randomisation
22. Infant already diagnosed with food allergy at the time of randomisation
23. Age intervention began (e.g. no of days between birth and randomisation)
24. *FLG* genotype (method of analysis and what *FLG* mutations were genotyped)
25. Ethnicity
26. Mode of delivery (e.g. caesarean, vaginal)
27. Method of feeding (e.g. Breastfeeding at all time points recorded)
28. Any additional trial randomisation stratification factors

Family baseline characteristics:

29. Age of mother at randomisation or enrolment
30. Age of father at randomisation or enrolment
31. Ethnicity of mother
32. Ethnicity of father
33. Educational status of mother
34. Educational status of father
35. Socioeconomic group
36. Singleton or multiple pregnancy
37. Number of other children living at home (without new child – or indicate if this includes the new child)
38. Whether any cats living in the household/living environment?
39. Whether any dogs living in the household/living environment?
40. Mother took any antibiotics during pregnancy?
41. Mother took any regular probiotic supplements during pregnancy?
42. Smoking status of mother
43. Smoking status of father

Family history of atopic disease:

44. Number of first degree relatives with atopic disease (0, 1 or more)[†] [Please indicate how atopic disease is defined]
45. Number of first degree relatives with eczema (0, 1 or more).
46. Number of first degree relatives with food allergy (0, 1 or more).
47. Number of first degree relatives with asthma (0, 1 or more).
48. Number of first degree relatives with rhinitis/hay fever (0, 1 or more).

Compliance data

49. Data on compliance with intervention. Including measures such as grams per day and total number of grams of product dispensed over the study.
50. Duration of treatment
51. Dates of treatment withdrawal and reason(s) for treatment withdrawal.

Non-assigned Skin care

52. Frequency of bathing
53. Product used for bathing (if not part of intervention)
54. Prescribed topical treatment use
55. Any other skin treatments

For cluster randomised trials:

56. Cluster randomisation factors

Food introduction:

57. Any data on the time/age when allergenic foods were introduced
58. Any data on the time/age when solid foods were introduced

*6, 7, 8 and 9 refer to adverse events of interest. All adverse events may be sent if trials do not have these separated out. [†]Critical baseline variables required for covariate adjustment within primary and secondary analyses.

Appendix 3 – Dummy tables and figures

Table A1 - Characteristics of included studies

Study	Setting	Methods	Participants	Intervention(s)	Length of follow-up	Outcomes	Funding source & COI	Notes
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Table A2 – Characteristics of included participants

Characteristic	Study 1	Study 2	Study 3	Study 4	Study 5	Study 6	Study 7	Study 8	Study 9	Study 10
Infant characteristics										
Gestational age at birth										
Sex										
Birth weight										
Mode of delivery										
Age intervention began										
<i>FLG</i> genotype (1, 2 or no mutations detected)										
Method of feeding										
Family characteristics										
Age of mother										
Age of father										
Ethnicity of mother										
Ethnicity of father										
Educational status of mother										
Educational status of father										
Socioeconomic group										
Singleton/multiple pregnancy										
No. children living at home										
Any cats at home										
Any dogs at home										
Mother took at least 1 course of systemic antibiotics during pregnancy										
Mother took regular probiotic supplements during pregnancy										
Mothers smoking status										
Fathers smoking status										
Family history of atopic disease										

No. first degree relatives
with atopic disease (0, 1+)
No. of first degree relatives
with eczema (0, 1+)
No. of first degree relatives
with food-allergy (0, 1+)

**Compliance with
randomised intervention‡**

Non-assigned skin care

Frequency of bathing
Prescribed topical
treatment use
Other

Food introduction

Age allergenic foods
introduced
Age solid foods introduced

‡Data summary will be informed by the available data.

Table A3 – Example Risk of bias table for a single study

Risk of bias due to	Judgement	Support for judgement
Randomisation process		
Deviations from interventions		
Missing outcome (outcome 1)		
Missing outcome (outcome 2)		
⋮		
Measurement of the outcome (outcome 1)		
Measurement of the outcome (outcome 2)		
⋮		
Selection of the reported result (outcome 1)		
Selection of the reported result (outcome 2)		
⋮		

Figure A1 – Example funnel plot (using dummy data):

Figure A2 - Example forest plot for binary outcome comparisons (using dummy data):

Figure A3 - Example dummy forest plot for continuous outcome comparisons (using dummy data):

Figure A4 - Example dummy forest plot for time to event outcome comparisons (using dummy data):

Table A4 –Summary of finding table 1 and GRADE assessment

Outcome	Relative effect effect	95% CI	No. participants (studies)	Quality of evidence (GRADE)	Comments
All skin care interventions versus no treatment					
Eczema					
Food allergy					
Slippage accidents around the time of bathing or application of moisturise					
Skin infection during the intervention					
stinging or allergic reactions to moisturisers					
Time to onset of eczema					
Parent reported reaction to known food allergy					
Allergic sensation to food allergen					

The table will include primary estimates of treatment effects in addition to the effect of complying with the intervention for the primary outcomes. We plan to include outcomes for sensitivity and subgroup analyses in the 'Comments' box at the bottom of 'Summary of Findings' in the Cochrane publication., so that if there are important findings there, they can be commented on with the relevant risk ratio in the Abstract

Table A5 – Serious adverse events summary - Number of participants and number of events by study

Study	Intervention No. of participants reporting serious adverse event	No. of serious adverse events reported	Control No. of participants reporting serious adverse event	No. of serious adverse events reported
Control = no treatment				
Study 1 (N=)				
Study 2 (N=)				
Study 3 (N=)				
Study 4 (N=)				
Study 5 (N=)				
⋮				
Control = other active intervention				
Study 1 (N=)				
Study 2 (N=)				
Study 3 (N=)				
Study 4 (N=)				
Study 5 (N=)				
⋮				

Table A6 – Serious adverse event details

Serious adverse event	No. of trials reporting serious adverse event	Intervention		Control	
		No. of participants reporting serious adverse event	No. of serious adverse events reported	No. of participants reporting serious adverse event	No. of serious adverse events reported
Control = no treatment					
	Event 1				
	Event 2				
	Event 3				
	Event 4				
	Event 5				
	⋮				
Control = other active intervention					
	Event 1				
	Event 2				
	Event 3				
	Event 4				
	Event 5				
	⋮				

Table A7 – Proportion with eczema over time

Study	N subjects	3mo		6mo		12mo		18mo		24mo	
		Int. %	Cont. %								
Control = no treatment											
	Study 1										
	Study 2										
	Study 3										
	Study 4										
	Study 5										
	⋮										
Control = other active intervention											
	Study 1										
	Study 2										
	Study 3										
	Study 4										
	Study 5										
	⋮										

Table A8 – Parent reported immediate reactions

Outcome	N trials	Pooled Treatment effect	95% CI	P value*
All interventions versus no treatment				
Milk				
Egg				
Peanut				
Other food				
All interventions versus other active control				
Milk				
Egg				
Peanut				
Other food				

*P-value for heterogeneity

Table A9 – Allergic sensitisation to foods and inhalants

Outcome	N trials	Pooled Treatment effect	95% CI	P value*
All interventions versus no treatment				
Any Food				
Any inhalant				
Any food or any inhalant				
All interventions versus other active control				
Any Food				
Any inhalant				
Any food or any inhalant				

*P-value for heterogeneity

Table A10 – Sensitivity analysis:

Outcome	Sensitivity analysis	N trials	Pooled RR (95% CI)	P-value ^Ø
All interventions versus no treatment				
Eczema [†]	Including studies at low risk of bias only			
	By eczema definition:	UK Working Party Criteria or other variations of the Hanifin and Rajka criteria only		
		doctor diagnosed eczema		
		parent report of eczema		
	Excluding/Including aggregate data*			
	Excluding non-prospectively acquired data			
	Excluding outlying studies [§]			
Food allergy [‡]	Including studies at low risk of bias only			
	By food allergy definition:	Oral food challenge		
		Investigator decision		
		Parent report of immediate reaction to common allergen		
	Excluding/Including aggregate data*			
	Excluding non-prospectively acquired data			
Excluding outlying studies [§]				

* Analysis will exclude/include aggregate studies that do not provide IPD based on the approach adopted for primary analysis. If aggregate data represents only an insignificant proportion of the dataset for example <10%, then the primary analysis will be on IPD data only, especially if the aggregate data trials are of poor quality. In this scenario we will undertake a sensitivity analysis adding in the aggregate data. Otherwise primary analysis will include IPD and aggregate data and sensitivity analyses will exclude the aggregate data. [§] Where considerable statistical heterogeneity is observed ($I^2 > 75%$) we will explore reasons for heterogeneity and where appropriate conduct sensitivity analysis excluding any studies identified as outlying. ^ØP-value for heterogeneity.

Table A11 - Subgroup analysis:

Outcome	Subgroup analysis	N Trials	Pooled Interaction effect (RR, 95% CI)	P value*
All interventions versus no treatment – patient characteristics				
Eczema [†]	Risk for atopy (high versus low - <i>FLG</i>) Risk for atopy (high versus low -family history) Risk for atopy (high versus low- <i>FLG</i> or family history)			
Food allergy [‡]	Risk for atopy (high versus low - <i>FLG</i>) Risk for atopy (high versus low -family history) Risk for atopy (high versus low- <i>FLG</i> or family history)			
All interventions versus no treatment – study characteristics				
Eczema [†]	Intervention timing (\leq first 4 weeks, > 4 weeks of life) Intervention duration (<6 months, \geq 6 months)			
Food allergy [‡]	Intervention timing (\leq first 4 weeks, > 4 weeks of life) Intervention duration (<6 months, \geq 6 months)			

[†]Measured as defined for the primary analysis of eczema. [‡] Measured as defined for the primary analysis of food allergy. *P-value for heterogeneity.

Table A12 –Summary of finding table 2 and GRADE assessment

Outcome	Relative effect effect	95% CI	No. participants (studies)	Quality of evidence (GRADE)	Comments
Skin care intervention A versus no treatment					
Eczema					
Food allergy					
Slippage accidents around the time of bathing or application of moisturise					
Skin infection during the intervention					
stinging or allergic reactions to moisturisers					
Time to onset of eczema					
Parent reported reaction to known food allergy					
Allergic sensation to food allergen					

Table will include Low risk of eczema and food allergy versus high risk of eczema and food allergy, either by *FLG* mutation or family history of allergic disease. We also plan to include outcomes for sensitivity and subgroup analyses in the 'Comments' box at the bottom of 'Summary of Findings' in the Cochrane publication.

Table A13 –Summary of finding table 3 and GRADE assessment

Outcome	Relative effect effect	95% CI	No. participants (studies)	Quality of evidence (GRADE)	Comments
All skin care intervention B versus no treatment					
Eczema					
Food allergy					
Slippage accidents around the time of bathing or application of moisturise					
Skin infection during the intervention					
stinging or allergic reactions to moisturisers					
Time to onset of eczema					
Parent reported reaction to known food allergy					
Allergic sensation to food allergen					

Table will include Low risk of eczema and food allergy versus high risk of eczema and food allergy, either by FLG mutation or family history of allergic disease. We also plan to include outcomes for sensitivity and subgroup analyses in the 'Comments' box at the bottom of 'Summary of Findings' in the Cochrane publication.